

Real-life study of the cost-effectiveness of benralizumab vs previous care in Bulgaria

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Abstract

The aim is to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of benralizumab therapy in real-life settings in Bulgaria in comparison with previous care. The point of view is that of the national health insurance fund, and the time horizon is for one year.

This study is based on findings from the BREEZE study for Bulgaria. 80 eligible patients with severe eosinophilic asthma were followed for 56 weeks after the initiation of the therapy with benralizumab. Pharmacotherapy costs pre- and post-initiation of benralizumab therapy were calculated. Outcome measurements were changes in the asthma control test (ACT), forced expiratory volume (FEV1), and the percentage of patients with exacerbations.

The mean pharmacotherapy cost was 3653.48 BGN before benralizumab and 19,581.69 BGN after benralizumab inclusion. Yearly costs for benralizumab per patient were estimated to be

5.35 times higher than previous therapy, amounting to 19,581.70 BGN vs. 3,653.48 BGN. Improvement in FEV1 leads to an incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) of 24,133.70 BGN (12,376.26 EUR). The incremental cost per avoided exacerbation was 22,046.90 BGN (11,304.10 EUR), and improvement in ACT resulted in an ICER of 1,146.33 BGN per point increase. Deterministic sensitivity analysis showed the highest ICER value of 2,392.52 BGN (1,266.93 EUR) per point improvement when benralizumab effectiveness decreased by 30% (ACT score = 16.89). Probabilistic sensitivity analysis showed 98.7% and 99.5% probability of cost-effectiveness below the thresholds of 1×GDP and 3×GDP per capita, respectively.

Benralizumab is cost-effective in comparison with previous care for patients with severe asthma based on real-life observation during the BREEZE study in Bulgaria from the point of view of a third-party payer.

Keywords

cost-effectiveness, asthma, real-life settings, benralizumab

Introduction

Asthma continues to be a major non-communicable disease that affects approximately 300 million people worldwide (GDB 2019). In the last decade, improvements in diagnosis, patient information, and health awareness, as well as novel therapeutic approaches, have led to improved

patient outcomes, asthma control, and a relative stabilization in prevalence (Porsbjerg et al. 2023). Nonetheless, severe uncontrolled asthma remains a challenge for physicians and healthcare authorities (Chung et al. 2014). Approximately 10% of asthma patients are estimated to suffer from severe, eosinophilic, uncontrolled asthma (To et al. 2012). The quest for disease control continues, with ad-

vances in recent years leading to the development of several new biological therapies for the treatment of severe refractory asthma (Jarjour et al. 2021). One of these molecules - benralizumab is authorized for treatment of severe refractory eosinophilic phenotype of asthma (Roboz and Rafii 1999; Koike et al. 2009; de Groot et al. 2015). The safety and efficacy of benralizumab were proven in 2 phase III randomized clinical trials (SIRROCO and CALIMA) (Bleecker et al. 2016; FitzGerald et al. 2016). These clinical trials highlighted some major benefits of therapy in patients with peripheral blood absolute eosinophil counts of 300 cells/ μ L or greater and in patients with frequent exacerbations (three or more). Most notably, the decrease in oral corticosteroid use and number of exacerbations were pointed out as outcomes with economic consequences for both the patients and society (Nair et al. 2017).

Recent real-world clinical studies have confirmed some of this observed benefit and extended it to show significant improvement in FEV1 (Kavanagh et al. 2021). Moreover, the reduction in exacerbations seems to be present even in non-naïve biologic patients, as reported by the ZEPHYR study in the US (Carstens et al. 2023). Despite this, there is still a noticeable lack of real-life evidence. To address this gap in knowledge, the BREEZE study, a multicenter, multinational real-life study, was approved and conducted in the countries of Central and Eastern Europe, as well as the Baltic states (Mihaltan et al. 2025). The study sought to characterize clinicopathological characteristics, treatment patterns, and treatment outcomes in patients with severe eosinophilic asthma receiving benralizumab. One of the countries included in BREEZE was Bulgaria. Data for the Bulgarian cohort confirmed a significant improvement in patient FEV1, asthma control test (ACT) scores, and number of exacerbations. Based on these results from the BREEZE Bulgarian cohort, we hypothesized that this would lead to extremely favorable cost-effectiveness ratios, despite the high cost of biologic therapy.

The aim of the study is to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of benralizumab therapy in real-life settings in Bulgaria in comparison with previous care. The point of view is that of the national health insurance fund, and the time horizon is for one year.

Methodology

This study is based on findings from the BREEZE study for Bulgaria. The BREEZE study was an observational multicenter study of pre-post design performed in real-life conditions. The design of the BREEZE study is described elsewhere, but in general, 80 eligible patients with severe eosinophilic asthma in Bulgaria were followed for 56 weeks after the initiation of the therapy with benralizumab (Mihaltan et al. 2025). The day on which benralizumab was first administered was taken as the index date. Retrospective data were collected – demographic, disease, and treatment characteristics data for the previous year – and then prospectively recorded for the follow-up period

during the next year. The report for the Bulgarian cohort was provided by AstraZeneca Bulgaria.

Cost analysis

Pharmacotherapy costs pre- and post-initiation of benralizumab therapy were calculated based on the recorded pharmacotherapy pre- and post-follow-up and the officially published list prices in the national positive drug list (PDL) (NCPRM 2024). The number of patients on a particular therapy and dosage regime was multiplied by the price of the product, and thus the yearly cost per patient was summarized. Reference prices, which are the lowest prices per defined daily dose (DDD), were considered for cost calculations. Costs were averaged out per patient per month as well as per patient per year. All costs are presented in Bulgarian currency (BGN) at the exchange rate of 1 EUR = 1.95 BGN.

Outcomes measurement

Three outcome measurements were selected from the BREEZE report – asthma control test (ACT), forced expiratory volume (FEV1), and percentage share of patients with exacerbations. Due to the varying number of patients during the follow-up period, data uncertainties were high, which prompted us to look at average scores over the follow-up period for parametric or median scores for non-parametric variables. The choice of the exacerbation rate is based on the evidence from the subgroup phase three clinical trial CALIMA showing a remarkable decrease in the exacerbation rate in patients with 2–3 exacerbations per year (Bleecker et al. 2016). Age-standardized lung function was unavailable from the report, only point and interval estimates.

Cost-effectiveness analysis

Incremental cost-effectiveness ratios were calculated for all outcome measures according to the following formula:

$$\frac{\text{Costs Benralizumab} - \text{Costs Alternatives}}{\text{Outcomes benralizumab} - \text{Outcomes Alternative}} = \frac{\Delta \text{Costs}}{\Delta \text{Outcome}}$$

ICER considered the average yearly cost of pharmacotherapy after benralizumab initiation – the average yearly cost of pharmacotherapy before benralizumab initiation, as well as the reported mean and median outcome measures.

Sensitivity analysis

As per good modeling practices (Caro et al. 2012), deterministic and probabilistic sensitivity analyses were conducted. Robustness of results was tested through deterministic sensitivity analysis by varying the cost and results within increments of +/-5%, 15%, and 30%. A probabilistic Monte Carlo simulation was conducted for a time horizon of 1 year (52 weeks, as the follow-up protocol in

the BREEZE study was 56 weeks). Values from the study were transferred to Excel, and probabilistic distributions were calculated with the inverse gamma distribution for costs, inverse beta distribution for positive change in FEV₁, and percentage share of patients experiencing exacerbations, inverse random probability for improvement in ACT score, as well as random probability of ACT score at the start of follow-up. A simple Excel macro was written to test for 5,000 iterations of the ICER coefficient. Results were graphed with the corresponding willingness to pay and distribution cloud against the threshold values of one time or three times the GDP per Capita.

Results

Cost estimation

Retrospective therapy data were available for 80 patients at the index date. The study began with 80 people, of whom 33 finished with a full set of data for their alternative pharmacotherapy and exacerbation rate (Table 1). Eleven patients treated with either mepolizumab or omalizumab were switched to benralizumab after study initiation. As a percentage share of patients, the most notable reduction in drug utilization was observed for patients treated with

montelukast. In total, three patients discontinued a drug – two patients discontinued their oral corticosteroids (OCS), while one patient discontinued theophylline. All patients continued their reliever therapy with salbutamol.

In general, mean and median costs per patient for non-biologic therapy did not differ (Table 2), and no significant difference was observed. Including the prices of biological therapy resulted in a mean cost of 3,653.48 BGN before benralizumab and 19,581.69 BGN after benralizumab inclusion.

The total yearly costs for the benralizumab cohort were calculated to be 1,581,331.95 BGN (807,626 EUR). It was calculated by multiplying the number of patients by the number of yearly prescribed injections and the price per injection (Table 3). The number of prescribed injections differs due to different patient states and was determined by treating physicians. Physicians reported only one patient who discontinued benralizumab therapy due to lack of therapeutic effect. The official list price for Benralizumab is 3,194.61 BGN.

A summary of calculated and reported monthly costs can be viewed in Table 4. Overall, the inclusion of benralizumab in the reimbursement lists leads to increased costs, which can be attributed mainly to the higher list price; however, a notable decrease in concomitant medication can be observed, as evidenced by Table 2.

Table 1. Yearly pharmacotherapy cost before and after benralizumab initiation.

Major concomitant respiratory treatment classes used for severe asthma	Before benralizumab initiation		At the end of the follow up		
	Dose regime	N People (%)	Yearly cost (BGN)	N People (%)	Yearly cost (BGN)
Maintenance oral corticosteroids (OCS)					
Hydrocortisone	15mg/day	2 (2.5%)	7,325.28		
Methylprednisolone	10mg/day	4 (5%)	144	1 (3%)	36
Prednisolone	40mg/day	2 (2.5%)	72	2 (6%)	72
Prednisone	16mg/day	10 (12.5%)	360	1 (3%)	36
OCS discontinuation for 1 year					
Inhaled corticosteroids and long-acting beta2-agonist bronchodilator (ICS + LABA) combination					
Beclomethasone / formoterol	400/24mcg/day	20 (25%)	9,540.40	10 (30%)	4,770.20
Budesonide / formoterol	640/18mcg/day	36 (45%)	455.16	11 (33%)	5,006.76
Fluticasone furoate / vilanterol	184/22mcg/day	10 (12.5%)	751.44	7 (21.2 %)	5,260.08
Fluticasone propionate / formoterol	500/20mcg/day	6 (7.5%)	7,015.68	2 (6%)	633.60
Fluticasone propionate / salmeterol	1000/100mcg/day	7 (8.75%)	2,217.60	3 (9%)	950.40
Inhaled corticosteroids (ICS) in monotherapy					
Budesonide	800mcg/day	1	455.16	1	455.16
Fluticasone propionate	500mcg/day	1	455.16	1	455.16
Long-acting beta2-agonist bronchodilator (LABA) in monotherapy					
salbutamol		80	3,398.40	33	1,401.84
Long-acting muscarinic antagonist (LAMA)					
Tiotropium	5mcg/day	74	51,326.40	31	21,501.60
Leukotriene Receptor Antagonist (LTRA)					
Montelukast	10mg/day	19(23.75%)	2,033.76	1 (3%)	107.04
Theophylline	600mg/day	1	693.60	0	Discontinue
Biologics (non-benralizumab)					
mepolizumab	100mg	1	17,768.88		
omalizumab	600mg	10	18,8265.60		

Table 2. Mean and median costs per patient with and without biologic therapy (BGN).

	Before benralizumab		After benralizumab	
	Mean	Median	Mean	Median
Costs per patient per year (w/o biologic therapy)	1,078.05	751	1,232.90	633.60
Costs per patient per year (with biologic therapy)	3,653.48	2,033.76	19,581.69	8,048.82

Table 3. Prescribed injections and cost of benralizumab therapy.

Injection N	People n	%	Total costs for all patients per # injections (BGN)
1	9	11.25	28,751.49
2	4	5	25,556.88
3	5	6.25	47,919.15
4	7	8.75	89,449.08
5	5	6.25	79,865.25
6	5	6.25	95,838.30
7	11	13.75	245,984.97
8	3	3.75	76,670.64
9	31	38.75	891,296.19

Results from the outcome analysis

FEV1 as an outcome

Based on the reported outcomes from the Breeze study, an average weighted improvement in lung function was calculated (Table 5). The choice for this was based on the decreasing number of patients who were followed up. Regardless, a noticeable improvement in lung function was observed. Uniquely, a patient was recorded in week 16 as having a maximum volume of 4.44 L, which isn't observable during the following weeks, likely due to failure to follow up.

Exacerbations and their frequency as an outcome measure

During the previous year before the initiation of the benralizumab therapy, a total of 229 (SD = 2.862) exacerbations were recorded. The mean number of overall exacerbations was 3.1 (SD = 1.47). Roughly 74% (n = 59) of patients reported exacerbations, with 82.5% of patients being hospitalized due to an exacerbation. During the follow-up period, a remarkable decrease in the number and rate of exacerbations was reported (Table 6). Across all weeks of follow-up, between 1.37% and 2.22% of patients (n = 1) reported at least one exacerbation. The drop-down of the patients is probably due to the fact that part of the observation period overlaps with COVID-19 infection, and some of the patients could not report all the data. At week 48 of follow-up, all 33 patients reported no exacerbations.

None of the reported exacerbations in that single patient required hospitalization; thus, in relative efficacy, a 71.3% reduction in overall exacerbation rate could be established – from 74% to 1.73% (Table 7). Following these measurements, the probability distributions of any exacerbations were estimated to vary between 20% and 82.5% for alternative therapies and between 1.37% and 2.09% for benralizumab.

Asthma control test (ACT) as an outcome measure

The most notable and relevant improvements were observed in ACT scores. Similarly to FEV1, a gradual decline in the number of observed patients was observed, prompting us to calculate the weighted average. However, improvements in overall scores were observable from week 16 onward, with the mean improvement measured at +13.89 points (Table 8).

Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio

Cost per 100 mL improvement in expiratory volume

Yearly costs per patient for benralizumab were estimated to be 5.35 times higher than previous therapy (Table 9), amounting to 19,581.70 BGN vs. 3,653.48 BGN. Accounting for the improvement in FEV1 leads to an incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) of 24,133.70 BGN (12,376.26 EUR), which is just below the 1 times GDP per capita threshold of 28,516.81 BGN. There is no explicitly stated threshold value for Bulgaria, but authorities recommend the World Health Organization (WHO) threshold of 3 times gross domestic product (GDP) per capita (Thokala et al. 2018). In 2023 the GDP per capita was 28,516 BGN (14,580 EUR) (NSI 2024). Therefore, the ICER is below the GDP per capita, meaning that benralizumab is a highly cost-effective therapy for the Bulgarian healthcare payer per 100 mL improvement in lung function.

The robustness of results was tested through deterministic and probabilistic sensitivity analyses. Due to the relatively small increase in results and higher average cost for benralizumab, the two factors with the largest impact on the ICER were either a 30% improvement in outcomes of alternative therapies to benralizumab, or a 30% decrease in benralizumab effectiveness (Fig. 1). A higher efficacy for alternative therapies results in an ICER of 74,780.33 BGN, which is still below 3 times the GDP threshold; however, a substantial decrease in benralizumab effectiveness of -30% (or 1.5 L in FEV1) results in an unsustainable threshold of 1 million BGN per 100 mL. All other variations resulted in acceptable ICER coefficients.

A Monte Carlo simulation with 5000 ICER calculations, following the established probability distributions, showed a 95.15% probability that the ratio will be lower than 3 times GDP per capita and an 84.14% probability it will be below the threshold of 1 times GDP per capita (Fig. 2). The average probability of benralizumab being cost-saving is 5.7%.

Table 4. Model inclusion costs.

	Min.	1 st Qu.	Median	Mean	3 rd Qu.	Max.
Monthly cost per patient with benralizumab	2,670.48	3,509.06	8,846.73	19,581.69	5,785.22	28,751.49
Monthly costs per patient without benralizumab	72	455.16	2,033.76	17,192.85	7,879.06	18,265.60

Table 5. Average weighted improvement in lung function.

	n	Min.	1 st Qu.	Median	Mean	3 rd Qu.	Max.	St. Dev.	95% CI	95% CI
FEV1 at index (L)	65	0.69	1.07	1.31	1.49	1.79	3.71	0.60	1.30	1.68
Weighted improvement in FEV1	37	1.15	1.59	1.89	2.15	2.56	3.56	0.80	1.53	2.76
FEV 1 (week 16)	15	0.57	1.6	1.70	2.33	3.06	4.44	1.09	1.80	2.85
FEV 1 (week 24)	11	1.2	1.34	1.95	2.09	2.43	3.90	0.83	1.55	2.63
FEV 1 (week 48)	7	1.35	1.44	1.74	1.87	2.28	2.52	0.49	1.35	2.38
FEV 1 (week 56)	4	1.49	1.99	2.17	2.31	2.50	3.41	0.8	1.43	3.18

Table 6. Distribution of number of events by type of exacerbation at baseline (1 year prior to benralizumab start).

	n	Min.	1 st Qu.	Median	Mean	3 rd Qu.	Max.	St.Dev.
Exacerbations leading to increase of the stable background dose of OCS	14	1	1	1	1.71	2.75	4	1.07
Exacerbations needing systemic corticosteroids for three days or more	64	1	1	2	2.38	3.00	6	1.28
Exacerbations leading to ER presentation	16	1	1	1	1.25	1.00	3	0.58
Exacerbations leading to hospitalizations	66	1	1	1	1.24	1.00	3	0.50
Overall exacerbations	59	1	2	3	3.10	4.00	7	1.47

Table 7. Exacerbations during the benralizumab therapy.

Overall Exacerbations	Week 4	Week 8	Week 16	Week 24	Week 32	Week 40	Week 48
None	72 (98.63%)	69 (98.57%)	62 (98.41%)	53 (98.15%)	49 (98.00%)	44 (97.78%)	33 (100%)
Yes	1 (1.37%)	1 (1.43%)	1 (1.59%)	1 (2.00%)	1 (2.00%)	1 (2.22%)	0

Table 8. Patients' ACT test scores during follow-up.

	n	Min.	1 st Qu.	Median	Mean	3 rd Qu.	Max.	St. Dev.	95% CI	95% CI
ACT at baseline	77	6	9	10	10.23	12	20	2.43	9.88	10.58
Weighted average	33	22	23.44	25	24.13	25	25	1.225	23.75	24.50
ACT (w16)	14	21	25	25	24.5	25	25	1.29	23.8	25.2
ACT (w24)	9	20	21	25	23	25	25	2.06	21.4	24.6
ACT (w48)	6	22	22.75	25	24	25	25	1.55	22.4	25.6
ACT (W56)	4	25	25	25	25	25	25	0	25	25

Table 9. Base Case ICER per 100 ml improvement in forced expiratory volume (FEV₁).

	Yearly per patient costs	Mean Lung Function per patient	Δ Cost	Δ Results	ICER
Before benralizumab	3,653.48 BGN (1,837.58 EUR)	1.49 L			
After benralizumab	19,581.69 BGN (10,041.89EUR)	2.15 L	15,928.20 BGN (8,168.31EUR)	0.66 L	24,133.70 BGN (12,376.26EUR)

Cost-effectiveness of prevented exacerbation

Benralizumab therapy is more expensive, but patients experience a significantly lower number of exacerbations. Calculating ICER values for percentages meant that costs had to be multiplied by 100 to calculate the ratio between additional costs per number of avoided exacerbations (Table 10). The incremental cost per avoided exacerbation was 22,046.90 BGN (11,304.10 EUR) per year, well below the lowest possible threshold.

The deterministic sensitivity analysis showed that varying the costs or outcomes of benralizumab are the biggest drivers of variation in the ICER. Nonetheless, even in extreme cases the ratio was well below threshold levels, indicating an extremely favorable cost-effectiveness profile for the national health-care systems. Maximum ICER values were 31,818.24 BGN, while the minimum was 13,913.23 BGN. This is mainly due to the high effectiveness and low probability of exacerbation within the year observed in the benralizumab cohort.

Figure 1. Deterministic analysis of costs and FEV outcomes: benralizumab vs. alternatives.

Figure 2. Monte Carlo simulation for lung function as an outcome.

Table 10. Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio.

	Yearly costs per 100 patients	Number of exacerbations per 100	Δ Cost	Δ Results	ICER
Before benralizumab		74			
After benralizumab	1,958,169.27 BGN (187,358.03 EUR)	1.74	1,592,821.12 BGN (816,831.34 EUR)	72.26	22,046.90 BGN (11,304.10 EUR)

Due to the high variability in recorded exacerbations in the cohort before the introduction of benralizumab (between 20% and 82.5%), the calculated probabilistic dispersion cloud showed high variability. Overall, the probability that benralizumab was cost-effective below the 3× GDP threshold was 97.46 %, and 70.78% for below the 1× GDP threshold. The probability it would be cost-saving was calculated to be 25.04% (Fig. 3). The maximum ICER coefficient was 145,444.90 per avoided exacerbation, and the minimum was 69,125 BGN per avoided exacerbation.

Cost-effectiveness per point increase in ACT score

The observed improvement in ACT results for patients on benralizumab resulted in an ICER of 1,146.33 BGN per point increase (Table 11). Results were robust and favorable for the cost-effectiveness profile. Deterministic sensitivity analysis showed the highest ICER value of 2,392.52 BGN (1,266.93 EUR) per point improvement when benralizumab effectiveness decreased by 30% (ACT score = 16.89). Lowest ICER value calculated was 723.55 BGN (371.05 EUR) – Fig. 5. Probabilistic sensitivity analysis showed 98.7% and 99.5% probability of cost-effectiveness below the thresholds of 1×GDP and 3×GDP per capita, respectively (Fig. 6).

Discussion

In this study we attempted to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of benralizumab in real-life settings in Bulgaria based on the results of the BREEZE study. We found out that benralizumab is a cost-effective alternative for the treatment of eligible patients with eosinophilic asthma.

Similar to our results, Spanish researchers found that after 1 year of treatment with benralizumab, patients with refractory eosinophilic asthma showed an improvement in all the measured effectiveness parameters. They reported that the total annual cost per patient was 14,043 EUR and that the ICER is 602 EUR per avoided exacerbation (Padilla-Galo et al. 2021). Their study is also performed in real-life settings like ours, and this is the only real-life study till the middle of 2024.

Gonzalez-Barcalá analyzes the cost-effectiveness of mepolizumab with standard of care versus other biological therapies in Spain (Gonzales-Barcala et al. 2021). They found that mepolizumab is dominant to benralizumab and reslizumab. The other Spanish study comparing benralizumab, dupilimumab, and mepolizumab concluded that benralizumab can be considered as a dominant treatment (Mareque et al. 2023). Both Spanish studies were criticized because they were based on indirect comparison and do not include many confounding factors (Martinez-Moragon 2023).

Figure 3. Deterministic sensitivity analysis of costs per number of avoided exacerbations.

Table 11. Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio with ACT as an outcome measure.

	Yearly per patient costs	Weighted ACT score	Δ Cost	Δ Results	ICER
Before benralizumab	3,653.48 BGN (1,837.58 EUR)	10.230			
After benralizumab	19,581.69 BGN (10,041.89 EUR)	24.125	15,928.20 BGN (8,168.31 EUR)	13.895	1,146.33 BGN (587.86 EUR)

Figure 4. Probabilistic sensitivity analysis of costs per number of avoided exacerbations.

Figure 5. Deterministic sensitivity analysis ICER per point improvement in ACT score.

Cost-effectiveness analysis of benralizumab in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia led to the conclusion that benralizumab demonstrated higher QALYs gained per patient, as well as higher annual costs, when compared to standard care alone. Similarly, our study found that cost is mainly driven by drug acquisition costs (Idrees et al. 2023).

A study in Sweden based on three clinical trials of benralizumab concluded that benralizumab has a high probability of being cost-effective compared with the standard of care plus oral corticosteroids for a subgroup of patients with severe, eosinophilic asthma (Andersson 2020).

In Brazil, the cost-effectiveness of dupilumab, mepolizumab, and benralizumab for severe eosinophilic asthma was ex-

Figure 6. Probabilistic sensitivity analysis ICER per point improvement in ACT score.

plored, and it was concluded that dupilumab is cost-effective when compared to benralizumab and mepolizumab (Taminato et al. 2022). When our study was performed, we still did not have dupilumab available in the national market.

It is evident that real-life studies of benralizumab are scarce, which is a strength of our study. We can point out several limitations of our analysis. The first one is that it focuses only on the pharmacotherapy cost and does not calculate the changes in other healthcare resource utilization due to lack of sufficient data. The second limitation is that due to COVID-19 spread, only limited data for patients were available at the end of the first year. Nevertheless, we consider that our study is representative enough because patients with severe eosinophilic asthma are relatively limited in number.

Conclusion

Benralizumab is cost-effective in comparison with previous care for patients with severe asthma based on real-life observation during the BREEZE study in Bulgaria from the point of view of a third-party payer.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

Astra Zeneca Bulgaria provide the report for the Bulgarian cohort in this study and funded the publication of the results. The company does not influence in any other means the calculations of the costs, selection of the results measurement and cost-effectiveness analyses.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

KT – software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Data Curation, Writing – Original draft, Writing – Review and Editing. PM – software, Validation, Investigation, Resources, Data Curation, Writing – Original draft. GP – Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Supervision, Project administration, Writing – Original draft, Writing – Review and Editing, Funding Acquisition.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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